

From Strings to Streams: A Multi-Period Analysis of QKD over EONs, Showcasing Multi-Band vs. Multi-Fiber Solutions

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Abstract—Quantum key distribution over optical networks has been noted as a state-of-the-art approach to next-generation secure communication. We propose two approaches to manage the signal for quantum key exchange between two trusted nodes; in the first approach, the quantum channel (QCh) uses distinct fiber whereas the classic channel (CCh) and public interaction channel (PICh) use another fiber to be transmitted on C-band (C+L band), and in the second approach CCh and PICh are transmitted over C+L band and QCh only uses O-band, both routed on the same fiber. In this context, two variations of the initial approach have been put forth, namely scenario 1 and scenario 2. In scenario 1, the CChs are positioned within the extended C-band, while in scenario 2, they find their place within the extended C+L-band. Concerning the secondary approach, denoted as scenario 3, the CChs+PIChs and QChs are situated in the extended C+L-band and low-loss O-band with consideration of noises over QChs, respectively. We propose a heuristic resource allocation with a time-division multiplexing technique in quantum resource allocation to compare the resource utilization of the mentioned approaches. The simulation outcomes demonstrate the advantages of adopting scenario 3 in relation to fiber deployment. This is highlighted by an 86% (34%) enhancement in fiber efficiency when compared to scenario 1 (2), all while employing an equal count of quantum transmitters and receivers over the initial eight years. As per the specifications of scenario 3, during the concluding year, there has been a notable 44% surge in quantum transmitter and receiver utilization for both scenarios 1 and 2. This upsurge is accompanied by a substantial reduction in fiber utilization, amounting to a 117% (34%) reduction concerning scenario 1 (2).

Index Terms—Quantum Key Distribution (QKD), Elastic Optical Networks, multi-band

I. INTRODUCTION

The expansion of internet access and the proliferation of diverse requests have elevated security concerns, especially for highly sensitive data like personal and financial information [1]. Additionally, the rapid advancement of quantum computers poses a significant threat to the security of existing

information and communication technology systems, primarily due to the computational complexity of the underlying mathematical functions [2]. To address this challenge, the quantum realm itself offers a solution known as quantum key distribution (QKD), which relies on the fundamental principles of quantum mechanics, including Heisenberg’s uncertainty principle and the quantum no-cloning theorem, providing unconditional security [3]. Furthermore, to meet the demands for high flexibility, scalability, and enhanced spectrum efficiency, the concept of an elastic optical network (EON) has emerged as a promising architectural approach [4].

To establish QKD communication following the BB84 protocol, we require two additional channels in addition to the classical channel (CCh) [5]. The first of these channels is known as the quantum channel (QCh), responsible for transmitting photon polarization states for secret key transfer. The second channel serves the purpose of facilitating communication between the parties involved in key sharing, specifically Alice and Bob. In our paper, we refer to this channel as the public interaction channel (PICh). In the realm of quantum communication, two approaches are commonly employed: utilizing dark fiber for quantum communication or integrating both quantum and classical channels within a single fiber, referred to as coexistence [6], [7]. The latter approach presents unique challenges due to the lower power of quantum signals compared to classical signals [8], [9].

QKD network deployment over an optical transport network was first studied over a distinct fiber for Quantum and Classic signals. Several studies in this field have suggested heuristic and ILP strategies to address resource allocation in network design. In [10], a secret key assignment priority ordering policy was introduced to optimize the routing, wavelength, and time slot assignment for QKD requests. In [11], a resource assignment with a scheduling strategy to allocate network resources in QKD optical networks was proposed to mitigate quantum blocking as a quality of service parameter because of limited resources. To transport as many keys as feasible through the network and to ensure fair key distribution across all sources and destinations, the authors of [12] proposed a heuristic and ILP method. The authors of [6] focused on

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Fig. 1. (a) CCh+PICH (blue channels) over extended C+L-band and QCh (orange channels) over extended C-band using distinct fibers, (b) CCh+PICH over extended C+L-band and QCh over low-loss O-band both using the same fiber. GB: guard band, CCh: classical channel, PICH: public interaction channel, QCh: quantum channel.

solving the problem of multi-dimensional routing, wavelength, and time slot allocation by providing a time-window-based security orchestration method to effectively use resources and support services with various security needs in metro QKD networks. The next proposed solution for implementing QKD is to exploit multi-core fibers (MCFs), which was mentioned in [4]. The authors suggest using MCFs and space division multiplexing (SDM) methods to integrate QKD with EON and suggest a method for allocating network resources to maximize the SKR while minimizing the number of utilized frequency slots with the consumption of various noise sources over the quantum signal. In addition to effectively using current optical fiber infrastructures [13], the coexistence of quantum and classical in the same fiber has been proposed as an effective solution with the help of WDM technology. The authors of [14] emphasized the critical importance of effectively integrating QKD with dense wavelength division multiplexing. In [15], the emphasis was shifted to reducing the cost of QKD over WDM deployment in backbone networks with the coexistence of CCh and QCh in a single fiber; QCh was placed in the O-band with no noise and quality of transmission consideration. However, little progress has been made regarding the positioning of secure relays. The primary focus of the authors in [16] is the deployment of trusted nodes in backbone QKD networks, where trusted nodes are placed at preexisting in-line amplifier stations.

To the best of our knowledge, the O-band has not yet been utilized for QCh alongside fully loaded extended C+L band classical channels. Therefore, we propose, for the first time, a heuristic algorithm for resource allocation in a single fiber coexistence scenario, considering the placement of QChs in

the O-band or dedicating a separate fiber to the QChs. This approach takes into account impairments in quantum signals in detail and incorporates time-division multiplexing (TDM) techniques for quantum channels (PICH, QCh). The paper's contributions can be summarized as follows: (i) Analysis of rates in various coexistence scenarios of quantum and classical signals, comparing the achievable secret key rate (SKR) with effective noise and traditional optical capacity; (ii) Proposing two approaches to managing quantum signals for SKR optimization: utilizing separate fibers and utilizing the O-band spectrum. These approaches are comprehensively evaluated within the context of a network-wide study, considering factors such as fiber and quantum transmitter/receiver (Tx/Rx) usage; (iii) Presenting a heuristic algorithm for resource allocation that facilitates the grooming of classical traffic over time, while implementing the TDM technique for quantum channels.

The organization of this paper is as follows. In section II, we have explored the system model including node and network architectures, the noise sources on the quantum channels, and secret key rate analysis. Section III explains network and traffic model and proposed heuristic algorithm. Next, section IV discusses on simulation setup, network upgrading strategies, and the performance evaluation of the proposed heuristic algorithm in three scenarios along with a precise comparison between them. Finally, the paper has been concluded in section V.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A. Node and Network Architectures

Node architecture is represented in Fig. 1 to transfer keys and data by paying attention to the decoy state BB84 protocol [8]. For key exchange first QSS generates a weak photon and sends it to PF, next PF passes a string of single polarization photons (rectilinear or diagonal) based on a random number of RNG, and finally, Alice sends the quantum bits through QCh to Bob. On Bob's side first Bob receives the quantum bits and measures them randomly with two bases (rectilinear or diagonal). After these steps, a raw key will be generated between the QKD transceivers and a final key will be distilled from the raw key in the PICh manager block, following the rules settled between Alice and Bob [5]. In every intermediate node, we amplify the CCh signal according to the band, and PICh and QCh drop to share the key with the last node. The stored final key is used to encrypt or decrypt for sending or receiving data in the encryption/decryption block. According to the low SKR in long distances, we require trusted relays to share keys between source and destination so we chose the location of these relays based on the limitations of constructing new stations from the amplifying stations [16]. In this work, we considered two models for handling the signal in quantum key exchange between two reliable nodes. In the initial method shown in Fig. 1(a), the QCh employs a separate fiber, while the CCh and the PICh use a different fiber for transmission in the C+L-band. In the second method illustrated in Fig. 1(b), both the CCh and PICh are transmitted over the C+L band, while the QCh exclusively utilizes the O-band. These signals are all routed through a single fiber.

B. Noise on Quantum Channel

By using the decoy-state technique in QKD a finite number of photons is sent per pulse, which solves the limitation of an ideal single photon source [8]. In contrast, in classical signals, thousands of photons are sent per signal. The low-strength quantum signal experiences crosstalks and nonlinear effects due to the presence of high-power classical signals. The sources of crosstalk noise are Spontaneous Raman Scattering (SpRS) and adjacent channel cross talk [17]. Adjacent channel cross talk is power leakage on adjacent channels, which is caused by insufficient channel isolation; so by deploying a narrow-band filter (NBF) at the quantum receiver, the effect of this noise can be minimized. SpRS occurs when a CCh interacts inelastically with vibrational modes within a fiber. The quantum and classical signals travel in the same direction in dual-fiber systems, so only forward Raman must be considered. The forward SpRS power on a QCh is calculated from (1) [18],

$$P_{\text{SpRS}}^q = l \times \Delta\lambda_q \sum_{c=1}^N e^{-\alpha(f_c)l} p_c \rho(\lambda_c, \lambda_q) \quad (1)$$

where l is fiber length, $\alpha(f_c)$ is the fiber attenuation coefficient that depends on the channel frequency, i.e., f , N is the number of CChs, p_c is classical launch power, $\Delta\lambda_q$

is the bandwidth of the quantum channel filtering system, and $\rho(\lambda_c, \lambda_q)$ denotes Raman cross section with respect to the wavelength of quantum and classical signal. To avoid the Raman scattering spectrum peak around the classical source, a 200 GHz gap (approximately 1.6 nm) is required [4]. $\rho(\lambda_c, \lambda_q)$ for the higher wavelength of the classical signal pump (Stoke) is larger than the lower wavelength (anti-Stoke), so the quantum signal must be located at lower wavelengths. Another source of noise is four-wave mixing (FWM), which is generated due to the Kerr effect in the fiber. FWM and stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) impairments due to the non-linear interference (NLI) effect, which is the exact calculation of noise by a generalized Gaussian noise (GGN) model, are estimated by using GNPY module written in Python programming language [19]. However, the authors in [20]–[22] applied an approximate FWM model which does not consider the SRS effect; in this work, we apply a more accurate GN model, i.e., GGN by applying the GNPY [19]. In this context, the NLI power spectral density ($G_{\text{NLI}}(l, f)$) can be obtained from (2), where $G_{\text{TX}}(f)$ is power spectral density after transmission along a fiber with length l , γ is the non-linear coefficient, β_2 is dispersion parameter, β_3 is dispersion slope, and $\Psi(z, f)$ is the overall frequency and space-dependent fiber loss profile, which includes the non-flat fiber attenuation and the SRS derived from solving ordinary differential equations (ODEs) [23]. In addition, any noise caused by quantum interaction with each other is negligible, due to their low power. Lower-bound of SKR is determined based on the Shannon formula, by considering the background noise (dark current, NLI, and SpRS) [17], using (3),

$$\text{SKR} \geq \max \{0, (Q_1 [1 - H(e_1)] - \eta_{\text{ec}} Q_\mu H(E_\mu)) / T_s\} \quad (3)$$

where η_{ec} denotes the error correction inefficiency, H is the Shannon binary entropy, E_μ is quantum-BER (QBER), Q_μ is the overall gain, T_s is the laser pulse reception period, and μ is the average number of photons in quantum sent pulse and Q_1 , e_1 are the gain and error rate of the single photon states that are obtained from equations (14) and (15) in [17], respectively.

C. Secret Key Rate Analysis

In quantum-classic coexistence, noise affecting QChs increases significantly when the number of CChs (N) rises and leads to a point where the SKR becomes zero for a short distance (e.g., below 3 km) [4]. Indeed, the concurrent presence of CChs and QChs within the same fiber, occupying either the same or adjacent spectrum bands, in the context of long-haul networks, imposes limitations upon the attainable SKR and the classical optical throughput. This predicament can be framed as a necessitated trade-off wherein the prominence of one requires the sacrifice of the other. In light of this circumstance, we undertake the task of elucidating the rationale behind the imperative separation of QChs from CChs. This necessitates the exclusive transmission of QChs through either a distinct fiber medium or a far-away segregated frequency band from the CChs. To substantiate this assertion,

$$G_{\text{NLI}}(l, f) = \frac{16}{27} \cdot \gamma^2 \cdot \iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} G_{\text{TX}}(f_1) \cdot G_{\text{TX}}(f_2) \cdot G_{\text{TX}}(f_1 + f_2 - f) \cdot \left| \int_0^l \frac{\Psi(\zeta, f_1)\Psi(\zeta, f_1 + f_2 - f)\Psi(\zeta, f_2)}{\Psi(\zeta, f)} \right. \\ \left. \left(\exp(j4\pi^2(f_1 - f)(f_2 - f) \cdot [\beta_2 + \pi\beta_3(f_1 + f_2)]\zeta) \right) d\zeta \right|^2 df_1 df_2 \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2. Total secret key rate (SKR) in all quantum slots versus fiber length for case 1 (QChs over C-band on distinct fiber), case 2 (QChs over O-band + fully loaded CChs over C+L-band), case 3 (QChs over C+L-band + 25 CChs over the end wavelengths of L-band) and case 4 (QChs over C-band + fully loaded CChs over L-band). QCh: quantum channel, CCh: classic channel.

we present a comprehensive exposition of four paradigmatic cases.

In Fig. 2, we demonstrate the total SKR of overall QChs (sum of SKR of all QChs) for different lengths. In our simulations, we implement four cases: in case 1, we assign C-band in distinct fiber for quantum and total 480 QChs; in case 2, we fulfill the C+L band with CChs and the O-band with 236 QChs (frequencies with α (loss coefficient) ≤ 0.3 dB/km); in case 3, C-band is dedicated to quantum and L-band to classical signals, so locate 480 quantum and 80 classical channels; and finally, in case 4 we allocate 25 CChs at lower frequencies of L-band by employing 200 GHz guard band, and remaining slots over C+L are used for QChs (totally 794 QChs). The parameters used in the simulations are as follows: QChs are 12.5 GHz, CChs are 75 GHz, $p_c = 0$ dBm, quantum power = -80 dBm, $T_s = 250$ ps, $\eta_{ec} = 1.16$, $\mu = 0.5$ (optimum value [4]), time gate interval of the detector (T_d) is 100 ps, phase-distortion error probability (e_d) = 0.015, quantum efficiency of single-photon detector (η_d) = 0.3, receiver dark current count (p_{dark}) = 10^{-8} , $\gamma = 1.20$ 1/W/km, $\beta_2 = -22.317$ ps²/km, $\beta_3 = 0.1331$ ps³/km.

At lower distances (i.e., lower than 2 km), QChs have a rate, so the case with the most number of channels (case 3) has the maximum initial rate (120 Gbit/sec). In case 3 and case 4, it becomes evident that increasing the number of classical

channels imposes limitations on the achievable length of the SKR. Although C-band is assigned to QChs completely, by increasing 55 CChs in L-band, the total possible distance for having the least SKR has a decrement of 37 km and the maximum reach distance becomes 14 km (case 4). So the coexistence of quantum and classical channels in the same or adjacent spectrum bands is viable for scenarios with a limited number of CChs, but it restricts the SKR achievable and the classical optical throughput. In case 1 and case 2, there is no effect of classical signals and only fiber loss affects SKR; thus, lower fiber loss (case 1) provides higher total SKR at different distances and has a maximum reach distance of about 344 km, while SKR is zero at distances above 226 km by using O-band, (see Fig.2).

III. NETWORK-WIDE ANALYSIS

As revealed in Fig. 2, the main challenge in establishing QChs and CChs in the network simultaneously, is the strong impact of the noise on QChs due to the high-power CChs. To tackle this problem, we analyzed two potential solutions in this study: isolating QChs in a distinct fiber (see Fig. 1(a)) or utilizing O-band (see Fig. 1(b)). According to the rate formula expressed in section II-B, SKR decreases exponentially with distance, proportional to the loss coefficient, so QChs are positioned in the C-band of separated fiber; also, in the multi-band scenario, the portion of the O-band with attenuation coefficient less than 0.3 dB/km (i.e., 1342-1360 nm) is selected for QChs. Furthermore, to deal with classical traffic increments, one can consider the extended C+L spectrum [24], which has a capacity of 12 THz for CCh and PICH channels. There are N nodes and L links in the network graph ($G(N, L)$), each with as many fibers as is required to meet the demands. The frequency spectrum of each band which is assigned to CCh and PICH is divided into 75 GHz channels and each QCh has 12.5 GHz bandwidth. We use TDM technology in QCh and PICH to avoid the waste of QKD resources. We consider transparent data transfer, so for CCh paths, continuity constraints must be satisfied in spectrum assignment. We assume all intermediate nodes and spans are trusted [16], [25]; so, for every QKD path, intermediate nodes and spans along the path share the secret keys between themselves in order to share the secret key between the source and destination [26]. Therefore, there is no need to satisfy the continuity constraint in spectrum assignment for QChs and PICHs. In order to save fiber consumption and quantum Tx/Rx between the two trusted nodes, quantum photons are only sent in one direction between the two nodes. And, the final key is shared according to the PICH channel considerations

Fig. 3. The proposed heuristic algorithm

between them. As a result, for the transmission of quantum photons in the multi-fiber strategy, only one fiber, and in the multi-band strategy, only one fiber in the fiber pair is allocated to the QCh. A semi-static scenario for the arrival of requests is assumed. taking into account service requests originating from different applications May feature distinct security needs for varying security levels [5] so, Each request is denoted by $R(s_r; d_r; \theta_r; \sigma_r; \tau_r)$, where s_r is the source, d_r is the destination, θ_r is classic traffic demand in GHz, σ_r is a binary variable and is 1 when demand needs quantum security, otherwise is 0. For demand with $\sigma_r = 1$, τ_r denotes key updating time. In the following, we consider three scenarios for network upgrading; **scenario 1** uses extended C-band (6 THz) for CCh and PICH over classic fiber pair and C-band for QCh over distinct fiber; **scenario 2** uses extended C+L-band (6+6 THz) for CCh and PICH over classic fiber pair and C-band for QCh over distinct fiber; finally, **scenario 3** uses extended C+L band for CChs and O-band for QCh using same fiber pair.

A. Heuristic Algorithm for Routing and Resource Assignments

We propose a heuristic algorithm for resource allocation in large-scale networks shown in Fig. 3. We use Yen's k-shortest path algorithm to pre-determine candidate paths for each source and destination. In classical channels, the first slot is assigned to PICH in all links of the network. Our

heuristic algorithm has two approaches depending on whether we have quantum security or not. For demands with quantum security, QCh routing, then these paths are examined and the path with a minimum channel number of used frequency and time slots is selected for spectrum and time slot assignment; and finally, classical demands are allocated as the same path of QCh with distance adaptive modulation assignment [27], [28]. We consider single-path grooming (i.e., same source, destination, and selected path) for resource allocation in the above-mentioned method. For demands without quantum security, first, we groom demands in a multi-path approach (i.e., only having the same source and destination node) and then assign channel slots to the path, which uses minimum channel index among k-shortest paths considering distance adaptive modulation assignment [27]. If a classical or quantum resource request is unavailable, we will reallocate the request from its source by adding fiber pairs or quantum transmitters and receivers to the busiest designated link of that path for that request.

IV. SIMULATION SETUP AND NUMERICAL RESULTS

We consider the national Deutsche Telekom (DT) topology with a maximum 50 km span length in each link [16]. The source and destination nodes of each traffic request are selected randomly. θ_r is chosen from 100-600 Gbps based on uniform distribution and σ_r is 0 (without quantum security)

Fig. 4. (a) Fiber length usage and normalized length (C: classic, Q: quantum) and (b) quantum Tx/Rx usage and SKR over 10 years for scenario 1 (classical and quantum over C-band using distinct fibers), scenario 2 (classic over C+L-band, quantum over C-band using distinct fibers), and scenario 3 (classic over C+L-band and quantum over O-band both using the same fiber).

with probability 0.25. The key length is 256 bits and the security level of the quantum key needed request is randomly chosen from the set $\{1, 2, 3\}$ corresponding to key updating time ($\tau_r \in \{256, 128, 64\}$) ms, respectively. In the initial year, the traffic throughput was 140 Tbps, and it increased by 35% every year. To compare the three existing scenarios, we first examined the amount of fiber length consumption in the network, which itself has a direct relationship with the number of fibers used, the amount of ROADMs utilization, and the degree of nodes. As illustrated in Fig. 4(a), scenario 1 has the highest fiber consumption since the classical channels are confined to the extended C-band, and an independent fiber is allocated for quantum data. Increasing the classical bandwidth of this scenario to extended C+L converts scenario 1 to scenario 2. Additionally, the bandwidth allocated for CCh and PICH on each added fiber is higher than that of scenario 1, resulting in a lower rate of fiber length consumption. As

a result, in year 10, we observed an 83% improvement with respect to scenario 1.

Furthermore, in scenario 3 considering that the increase in fiber was solely a consequence of the growing classical demands, and this scenario shares similar resources with scenario 2 in the classical domain; also, there is no need for distinct fiber from the quantum resource perspective, therefore scenario 3 has used about 4700 km less fiber in the first year, about 34% less percentage vs scenario 1 and 2 and has maintained this difference with scenario 2 until the last year, according to the explanations given. Finally, in the end, scenario 3 uses 117% less fiber compared to scenario 1 (see Fig. 4(a)). Considering the novel QKD technology causes significant Tx/Rx expenses; thus, it is crucial to evaluate their usage. As a result in the second part, we considered the results of the consumption of the number of quantum Tx/Rx to have a fair comparison between the three scenarios (see Fig. 4(b)). Due to the efficient allocation of quantum resources through TDM and high quantum key transmission rates, by using 105 Quantum Tx/Rx, none of the three scenarios have required an increase in quantum transmitters and receivers up to the 8th year. In scenario 3, due to higher attenuation in the O-band and in line with the exponential of increasing SKR requests, the utilization of quantum transmitters and receivers is respectively 12% and 44% higher than the other two scenarios in the last two years, which employed the strategy of placing quantum in a separate fiber.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have explored the constraints associated with the coexistence of CChs and QChs. Based on the SKR, by considering effective noise proportional to distance, we introduced a resource allocation algorithm for CChs and QChs by considering the time-division technique for quantum resource allocation. Finally, we conducted simulation scenarios for multi-band and multi-fiber cases. The numerical results show that while consuming equal Tx/Rx in scenario 3 compared to scenario 1 (2) up to the eighth year, there is 86% (34%) less fiber consumption, but in the ninth and tenth years, it is accompanied by an increase of 12% and 44% of quantum Tx/Rx, respectively. In general, the results indicate the superiority of scenario three, which is the placement of quantum signals in the O-band, over the use of separate fibers in the first eight years. However, this issue, given the exponential increase in the number of quantum Tx/Rxs in the last two years, requires an overall techno-economic evaluation of the proposed solution for future works.

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